

STUDIES IN CATALYTIC REACTIONS OF CHARCOAL. PART I. CATALYTIC OXIDATION AND DECOMPOSITION OF SALT SOLUTIONS

BY BALWANT RAI PURI, LEKH RAJ SHARMA AND D. D. SINGH

The catalytic oxidation of sodium nitrite, potassium arsenite, sodium sulphite and potassium ferrocyanide by atmospheric air and decomposition of sodium bicarbonate and sodium thiosulphate in the presence of the variously treated samples of sugar charcoal have been studied in some details. The maximum activity shown by the original sample has been ascribed to the presence of surface oxygen complex, capable of evolving carbon dioxide on degassing and of imparting acid character to the charcoal surface. A reasonable explanation for such reactions has been suggested.

Calvert (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1867, 20, 293) was probably the first investigator to demonstrate the catalytic oxidation of substances like alcohol, ethylene and hydrogen sulphide in the presence of charcoal. Feigl (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 119, 305) described similar catalytic oxidations of some inorganic salts. Krause (*Przemyst Chem.*, 1950, 29, 377) attributed the catalytic activity of charcoal to the presence of impurities such as compounds of iron, calcium and magnesium. Kolthoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4473) and King (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 889) studied the catalytic oxidation of potassium ferrocyanide by atmospheric air in the presence of charcoal, prepared from the same sample but activated severally at temperatures varying from 400° to 950°, and while the former reported that the maximum activity was associated with the sample activated at 900° and minimum with that activated at 400°, the latter found the reverse to be the case. The reason for these anomalous observations was that Kolthoff's oxidations were carried out in buffer solutions which counterbalanced the alkaline nature of the high-temperature activated charcoals. It was not realised that the acidity or alkalinity of surface might be an essential factor, affecting the course of such reactions. As regards the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide, it was found by King (*loc. cit.*) that maximum activity was associated with the sample activated at 850° and minimum with that activated at 400°.

Bente and Walton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1943, 47, 329) and Watanabe and Shiramoto (*J. Electrochem. Soc., Japan*, 1952, 20, 386) have also reported that the catalytic activity of charcoal depends upon the nature of the treatment given to it as well as the temperature and the reagents used for activation. The catalytic activity has also been ascribed by some workers (Feigl, *loc. cit.*; Brinkmann, *Angew. Chem.*, 1949, 61, 378; Courty, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1947, 642; *Compt. rend.*, 1945, 221, 27) to the film of adsorbed oxygen on the charcoal surface.

The influence which the oxygen complexes exercise on the surface behaviour of charcoal has been well known for some time (Puri *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 756; *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 50, 1071; King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1489; Weller and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 4155). Since catalytic reactions are, in the main, surface reactions, their study in the presence of charcoal, coated with different

types of oxygen complexes, is likely to be useful in elucidating the mechanism of such reactions. The present work was therefore undertaken with that end in view. It is divided into two parts; the first part describes the catalytic oxidation and decomposition of some inorganic salts in aqueous solutions and the second part deals with the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Charcoal samples.—A sample of sugar charcoal, prepared by the carbonisation of cane sugar by means of sulphuric acid followed by repeated washings with distilled water, was used. It was divided into three portions: one portion was used as such and was labelled as 'original charcoal'. The other two portions were degassed, one at 750° and the other at 1200°. The amounts of the chemisorbed gases present in each sample were determined by evacuating them at 1200° and analysing the gases evolved in the Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus. The results are recorded in Table I. It is seen that while the original sample contains oxygen disposed as CO and CO₂, that degassed at 750° contains oxygen disposed as CO only, and that degassed at 1200° does not contain any combined oxygen at all. The p_a value of the charcoal was seen to increase from 2.85 to 8.78 on degassing at increasing temperatures.

TABLE I

Amounts of gases evolved (mg./g.) on evacuating different samples of sugar charcoal at 1200° together with their p_a values.

Samples.	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ O.	H ₂ .	p_a values.
Original sample	13.27	13.12	10.34	14.96	2.85
Sample degassed at 750°	Nil	9.76	4.69	12.87	7.20
Sample degassed at 1200°	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	8.78

Procedure.—Each sample (1 g. portion) was shaken mechanically with 100 c.c. of 0.1N solution each of sodium nitrite, sodium sulphite, potassium arsenite, potassium ferrocyanide, sodium thiosulphate and sodium bicarbonate for different intervals of time after which an aliquot portion of the clear supernatant liquid was analysed by suitable volumetric methods. A blank run, without the addition of charcoal, was made simultaneously in every case.

TABLE II

Catalytic oxidation of sodium nitrite by different samples of sugar charcoal.

Time of shaking.	Percentage oxidation			
	Without charcoal.	With charcoal samples.		
		Original.	Degassed at 750°.	Degassed at 1200°.
2 hrs.	0.32	39.00	0.63	0.62
4	0.63	53.12	0.94	0.93
8	0.94	57.56	1.56	1.58
12	1.56	62.50	1.88	1.88
24	1.80	73.26	2.10	2.23

DISCUSSION

Taking the oxidation of sodium nitrite (Table II) in the first instance, it is seen that while in the absence of charcoal the reaction proceeds only to a small extent, in the presence of the original sample of charcoal, the reaction progresses considerably, the amount oxidised even within the first 2 hours being nearly 40% of the total amount of sodium nitrite taken. The reaction continues exponentially and within 12 hours more than 60% of the nitrite is oxidised. It may be mentioned that the amount of air contained in the empty space of the bottles, which remained corked during the reaction, was about 175 c.c. Thus, approximately 35 c.c. of oxygen was available for the reaction. This, as can be shown by simple calculations, could oxidise 6.4 m.e. (i.e. about 64% of the total amount added) of sodium nitrite only. The reason for the reaction to slow down after some time therefore appears to lie in the limited availability of oxygen. In a few experiments, the bottles containing the reaction mixtures were occasionally opened for a while to permit the frequent renewal of air. It was found that now practically the whole of the nitrite could be oxidised. It appears therefore that the original sample of charcoal, containing oxygen complexes (Table I), can initiate a sort of a chain reaction which progresses further and further with time provided that a sufficient amount of oxygen is available.

The charcoal sample, degassed at 750°, which contained some oxygen disposed as CO but none as CO₂, and that degassed at 1200°, which did not contain any combined oxygen at all, could not bring about this oxidation reaction to any noticeable extent (Table II). The *p_H* value of the original sample was 2.85 and those of the evacuated samples were 7.2 and 8.8. It appears that the acidic nature of the original charcoal is responsible for catalysing this reaction.

It has been shown (Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 357) that the original charcoal by virtue of the presence of CO₂-complex is capable of undergoing surface ionisation in water, as represented below :

It appears that surface hydrogen ions being directed towards the liquid phase react with sodium nitrite as :

The resulting nitrous acid then undergoes oxidation to nitric acid by atmospheric oxygen contained in the bottle. The nitric acid supplies more hydrogen ions and thus the reaction, initiated by surface hydrogen ions of charcoal, continues further till in course of time the entire amount of nitrite ions is oxidised to nitrate ions provided that a sufficient amount of oxygen is available for the purpose.

The *p_H* values of charcoal, left after the reaction (determined after washing and drying), were found to increase from 2.85 to 7.60 after 2 hours and to 9.25 after 12 hours from the commencement of the reaction. This is evidently due to the replacement of the surface hydrogen ions by sodium ions, as represented by the equation given

above, and confirms the conclusion already arrived at regarding the mechanism of the reaction.

Charcoal containing acidic surface should also be able to bring about the oxidation of other oxidisable salts. The results obtained with sodium sulphite, potassium arsenite and potassium ferrocyanide are presented in Table III. The reason for smaller oxidations of sodium sulphite and potassium arsenite lies in the fact that sulphurous acid and arsenious acid formed in these reactions cannot be oxidised so easily.

TABLE III

Catalytic oxidation of sodium sulphite, potassium arsenite and potassium ferrocyanide by the original sample of charcoal.

Time of shaking.	% O x i d a t i o n.			Time of shaking.	% O x i d a t i o n.		
	Na sulphite.	K arsenite.	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ .		Na sulphite.	K arsenite.	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ .
2 hrs.	Nil	4.80	3.00	2 days	12.92	...	8.70
4	..	5.48	4.21	3	14.60	8.22	11.13
8	1.12	6.38	5.70	5	...	10.27	...
12	2.82	6.85	6.26	10	...	13.29	...
24	7.39	...	6.94				

The oxidation of potassium ferrocyanide, represented by the equation,

should also be facilitated in the presence of original charcoal on account of its acid character and capacity to take up hydroxyl ions. The results in Table III show that this is actually the case. The evacuated samples of charcoal could not do so for obvious reasons.

If the mechanism proposed above for such reactions is correct, then the corresponding amounts of cations (Na⁺ or K⁺) should be fixed on the charcoal surface. This was verified by examining the charcoal left after the reaction. It was washed and dried in an electric oven maintained at 110°. A portion was then shaken with an excess of 0.1N-HCl. The amount of sodium (or potassium) chloride brought into solution was determined by evaporating the clear solution to complete dryness. The results obtained in a few experiments are shown in Table IV. It is evident that the amount of cation fixed on charcoal is almost exactly equivalent to the amount of the salt oxidised.

TABLE IV

Amounts of sodium nitrite and potassium ferrocyanide oxidised by 'original' sample and the cations fixed on charcoal surface.

Time of shaking.	Sodium nitrite.		Potassium ferrocyanide.	
	Amount oxidised.	Na ⁺ ions fixed on charcoal.	Amount oxidised.	K ⁺ ions fixed on charcoal.
2 hrs.	3.12 m.e./g.	2.97 m.e./g.	0.30 m.e./g.	...
4	4.25	4.33	0.42	0.45 m.e./g.
8	4.60	...	0.57	0.54
12	5.00	4.97	0.62	0.61
24	7.32	7.19	0.69	0.72
48	...	...	0.87	0.89
72	...	...	1.11	1.18

The surface hydrogen ions should also be able to bring about decomposition of salts like sodium thiosulphate and sodium bicarbonate, as represented below :

The data obtained by carrying out these reactions in closed bottles (Table V) show that this is actually the case. Evidently in these reactions no chain is set up and ultimately, when the surface hydrogen ions are replaced by alkali cations, the reactions should come to a stand-still, as has been found to be the case.

TABLE V

Catalytic decomposition of sodium thiosulphate and sodium bicarbonate by 'original' sample of sugar charcoal.

Time of shaking.	% Decomposition.		Time of shaking.	% Decomposition.	
	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	NaHCO ₃ .		Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	NaHCO ₃ .
12 hrs.	1.98	22.73	3 days	8.51	51.13
24	3.50	38.64	4	8.76	...
48	4.52	44.32	6	11.25	60.52

It may be noted that although the sample evacuated at 750° contains an appreciable amount of oxygen (Table I), it is not capable of bringing about any of these reactions. This is evidently due to the fact that the chemisorbed oxygen contained in it is not present as an acid oxide. The view expressed by some early workers (vide Feigl, Brinkmann, Courty, *loc. cit.*) that the activity of charcoal to oxidise or decompose salt solutions may be due to the existence of a film of chemisorbed oxygen, needs modification in-as-much as that it is only due to that part of the chemisorbed oxygen which on high temperature evacuation is evolved as carbon dioxide.